

Exploring Land Use/Land Cover Changes and Their Effect on Land Surface Temperature and Urban Heat Island: A Case of Lahore, Pakistan

Fahad Shah^{*1}

¹ Graduate School of Innovation and Practice for Smart Society, Hiroshima University, Japan

GISRUK 2026

Summary

This study examines land surface temperature (LST) dynamics and urban heat island (UHI) intensity in Lahore, Pakistan, using multi-temporal Landsat imagery from 2000 to 2020. Changes in land use/land cover (LULC), vegetation cover, and built-up density were analysed using Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI), and Urban Thermal Field Variance (UTFVI) indices. Results reveal rapid urban expansion accompanied by increasing LST and UHI intensity, with strong positive correlations between LST and built-up areas and negative correlations with vegetation. The findings highlight the importance of geospatial analysis for sustainable urban planning and climate-resilient city development.

KEYWORDS: Land Use/ Land Cover; Land Surface Temperature; Urban Heat Island; Urban Thermal Field Variance; Environmental Sustainability

1. Introduction

Urban and industrial expansions could contribute to infrastructure development, increased employment opportunities, and improved access to education and healthcare (Zhang et al., 2023). Still, they also bring about a slew of eco-environmental issues, such as overcrowding, strain on resources, global warming, air and water pollution, and the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect (Falihatkar et al., 2011). Urban areas commonly exhibit the UHI effect, a phenomenon characterised by higher temperatures compared to adjacent rural areas. This is primarily attributed to factors such as extensive impervious surfaces, limited vegetation cover, and the release of heat from human activities (Voogt and Oke, 2003, Shi et al., 2012). The UHI effect manifests through two primary mechanisms: Surface Urban Heat Island (SUHI), measured via land surface temperature (LST) using remote sensing techniques, and Atmospheric Urban Heat Island (AUHI), assessed through in-situ air temperature measurements (Berhane et al., 2018). These phenomena collectively increase energy consumption for cooling, degrade air quality, and pose significant health risks, particularly for vulnerable populations, including the elderly and outdoor workers (Burger et al., 2021, Yang et al., 2018).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area and Data

Lahore District is located in the northeastern part of Pakistan and represents a highly urbanised and climatically vulnerable region. Multi-temporal Landsat satellite images for the years 2000, 2010, and 2020 were obtained to analyse LULC and thermal characteristics. Ancillary data were used to support

* Fahadkahn333@mail.bnu.edu.cn

classification accuracy and spatial analysis.

2.2 Image Processing and Indices

Standard image pre-processing techniques, including radiometric and atmospheric correction, were applied. Supervised classification was performed to generate LULC maps. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) were computed to represent vegetation density and urbanisation intensity, respectively. Classification accuracy was evaluated using overall accuracy and the Kappa coefficient.

2.3 LST and UHI Estimation

Land Surface Temperature was retrieved from thermal bands using established radiative transfer equations. Urban Heat Island intensity was evaluated by comparing LST values across different land cover types. The Urban Thermal Field Variance Index (UTFVI) was used to assess ecological thermal stress levels within the study area.

2.4 Urban heat island

Urban heat island intensity was quantified using the normalized LST approach shown in Equation (1). In this formulation, T_s represents the pixel-wise land surface temperature, T_{mean} is the mean LST of the study area, and SD denotes the standard deviation of LST. The resulting UHI values are dimensionless, representing relative thermal anomalies with respect to the mean surface temperature, and are used for spatial comparison rather than absolute temperature measurement.

$$UHI = \left(\frac{T_s - T_{mean}}{SD} \right) \quad (1)$$

T_{mean} and T_s represent the average temperature and LST value obtained from a map and measured in Kelvin. The standard deviation is indicated by SD .

2.5 Urban thermal field variance index

UTFVI is a popular statistic for assessing the effects of UHI (Tomlinson et al., 2011). A variety of parameters affect the development of the UHI and UTFVI phenomena, including heat waves, psychometrics, surface change, and lighting intensity (Kafy et al., 2021). Equation (2) was used for calculating UTFVI. UTFVI is a dimensionless index derived from normalized LST values and is widely used to assess the spatial intensity of urban thermal stress.

$$UTFVI = \left(\frac{T_s - T_{mean}}{T_{mean}} \right) \quad (2)$$

Figure 1 flowchart for adopted methodology

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 LULC and LST Patterns

Results indicate a substantial increase in built-up areas from 22.99% in 2000 to 47.17% in 2020, accompanied by a decline in vegetation and agricultural land. Mean LST increased from approximately 33 °C in 2000 to 34.8 °C in 2020, reflecting intensified urban warming. Table 1 shows different statistics for different LULC classes. Figure 2 shows, the LULC change map.

Figure 2 LULC maps (a) 2000, (b) 2005, (c) 2010, (d) 2015 and (e) 2020

Table 1 Land use land cover types of overall results percentagewise from 2000-2020

Land cover types	Percent of total area (%) in different time points					
	2000	2005	2010	2015	2020	Net change
Water bodies	1.66	2.62	1.28	2.44	1.79	0.13
Agriculture land	53.21	65.04	53.75	57.69	46.16	-7.05
Barren land	22.14	4.62	8.9	2.11	4.88	-17.26
Built-up area	22.99	27.72	36.06	40.77	47.17	24.18

3.2 NDVI, NDBI, and UTFVI Analysis

Spatial analysis shows higher LST values in areas with dense built-up land and low vegetation cover. UTFVI results indicate increasing thermal stress in central urban zones, while peri-urban areas exhibit relatively lower thermal impact.

3.3 UHI Intensity and Correlation Analysis

The spatial analysis of UHI intensity across the selected benchmark years (2000 – 2020) reveals pronounced surface temperature contrasts between urban and non-urban areas, primarily associated with expansion and land surface modification (Fig. 3a-e). Throughout these 20 years, the central city, airport surroundings, and several industrial zones consistently exhibited higher UHI values, indicating intense anthropogenic heat accumulation and reduced vegetation cover.

In 2000 (Fig. 3a), UHI values ranged between 3.53°C and 19.66°C, reflecting moderate heat intensity concentrated mainly in the city core and emerging industrial clusters. The relatively lower thermal contrast in this period indicates limited built-up density and still prevailing green spaces. By 2005 (Fig. 3b), the UHI intensity increased sharply, with high values reaching 23.13°C, corresponding to rapid urban expansion, surface sealing, and loss of natural vegetation. A slight moderation occurred in 2010 (Fig. 3c), when the maximum UHI value was 22.14°C. Although some peripheral areas showed cooler zones, urban hotspots remained persistent in central and industrial sectors due to high energy consumption and vehicular emissions. The UHI peaked in 2015 (Fig. 10d) with a maximum of 26.40°C, highlighting the effect of extensive urban sprawl, increased impervious surfaces, and diminished evapotranspiration. These areas, especially around the central business district, airport, and industrial corridors, demonstrated the most severe heat accumulation. By 2020 (Fig. 3e), the maximum UHI intensity slightly declined to 18.61°C, with minimum values dropping to -7.92°C. This reduction may be attributed to the introduction of green cover, urban parks, and reflective construction materials in some localities. However, the persistence of high-temperature zones in central Lahore and along major transportation routes indicates that UHI effects remain a critical urban environmental issue.

Overall, the spatial dynamics from 2000 to 2020 reveal that urban expansion and land surface transformation are the primary drivers of increased UHI intensity in Lahore. Effective mitigation requires sustainable urban design, increased vegetation, and strategic land-use planning to reduce surface heating and enhance urban resilience. Together, the UHI and UTFVI results demonstrate that while UHI identifies where urban rural thermal contrasts are strongest, UTFVI highlights where thermal stress poses greater ecological and environmental risk.

Figure 3 Urban heat island maps from (a) 2000, (b) 2005, (c) 2010, (d) 2015 and (e) 2020

4. Conclusions

This study analyzed spatio-temporal LULC changes and their impacts on LST and UHI intensity in Lahore, Pakistan, from 2000 to 2020 using multi-temporal satellite-derived indices (LST, NDVI, NDBI, UHI, and UTFVI). The results indicate that rapid urban expansion, particularly in the city center, industrial areas, and airport vicinity, significantly increased surface temperatures, with built-up areas exhibiting 2–5 °C higher LST than surrounding vegetated and agricultural zones.

A strong positive relationship between LST and NDBI confirms the role of impervious surfaces in intensifying urban heating, while the negative correlation between NDVI and LST highlights the cooling effect of vegetation. Although some green cover expansion was observed, unplanned urbanization and population pressure led to an overall increase in LST, with a cumulative rise of approximately 1.8 °C over two decades. These findings emphasize the importance of preserving and expanding urban green infrastructure to mitigate UHI effects and improve urban thermal comfort.

Limitations of this study include the reliance on moderate-resolution satellite data, which may not fully capture fine-scale urban heterogeneity, and the exclusion of socio-economic factors, anthropogenic heat emissions, and in-situ meteorological observations that can influence urban thermal dynamics.

Overall, this study provides critical baseline information on LST and LULC interactions that can support urban planners and policymakers in developing sustainable land management strategies. Future research should integrate higher-resolution remote sensing data, ground-based temperature measurements, and socio-economic indicators to better quantify UHI drivers.

5 References

- BERHANE, T. M., LANE, C. R., WU, Q., AUTREY, B. C., ANENKHONOV, O. A., CHEPINOGA, V. V. & LIU, H. 2018. Decision-tree, rule-based, and random forest classification of high-resolution multispectral imagery for wetland mapping and inventory. *Remote sensing*, 10, 580.
- BURGER, M., GUBLER, M., HEINIMANN, A. & BRÖNNIMANN, S. 2021. Modelling the spatial pattern of heatwaves in the city of Bern using a land use regression approach. *Urban climate*, 38, 100885.
- FALAHATKAR, S., HOSSEINI, S. M. & SOFFIANIAN, A. R. 2011. The relationship between land cover changes and spatial-temporal dynamics of land surface temperature. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 4, 76-81.
- KAFY, A.-A., RAHMAN, M. S., ISLAM, M., AL RAKIB, A., ISLAM, M. A., KHAN, M. H. H., SIKDAR, M. S., SARKER, M. H. S., MAWA, J. & SATTAR, G. S. 2021. Prediction of seasonal urban thermal field variance index using machine learning algorithms in Cumilla, Bangladesh. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 64, 102542.
- SHI, B., TANG, C.-S., GAO, L., LIU, C. & WANG, B.-J. 2012. Observation and analysis of the urban heat island effect on soil in Nanjing, China. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 67, 215-229.
- TOMLINSON, C. J., CHAPMAN, L., THORNES, J. E. & BAKER, C. J. 2011. Including the urban heat island in spatial heat health risk assessment strategies: a case study for Birmingham, UK. *International journal of health geographics*, 10, 1-14.
- VOOGT, J. A. & OKE, T. R. 2003. Thermal remote sensing of urban climates. *Remote sensing of environment*, 86, 370-384.
- YANG, Y., NG, S. T., XU, F. J. & SKITMORE, M. 2018. Towards sustainable and resilient high density cities through better integration of infrastructure networks. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 42, 407-422.
- ZHANG, Z., ZHAO, M., ZHANG, Y. & FENG, Y. 2023. How does urbanization affect public health? New evidence from 175 countries worldwide. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 1096964.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the United States Geological Survey (USGS) for providing Landsat satellite data. We also thank the Government of Pakistan for the data.

Biographies

Fahad Shah is a PhD researcher at Hiroshima University. His research focuses on urban climate change, land surface temperature modelling, and the application of GIS and remote sensing techniques for sustainable urban development.

Google scholar account: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=nf6ZnYIAAAAJ&hl=en>